

Kuiji's Reinterpretation of Amitabha's Physicality: Implications for Yogācāra and Pure Land

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Abstract

This paper examines Kuiji's (632–682) *Forest of Meaning of the Three Bodies* as a sophisticated intervention in Tang-dynasty debates over buddha-body theory and the accessibility of Pure Lands, particularly that of Amitābha. Rather than approaching trikāya doctrine primarily through metaphysical speculation, Kuiji employs Sanskrit compound analysis, doctrinal synthesis, and hetuvidyā logic to clarify how different buddha-bodies are named, manifested, and perceived by distinct categories of practitioners. By analyzing Kuiji's grammatical treatment of terms such as *dharmakāya*, *saṃbhogakāya*, and *nirmāṇakāya*, the paper shows how linguistic structure functions as a hermeneutical tool that reshapes ontological assumptions about buddhahood and physicality. Kuiji's approach allows him to reconcile apparently conflicting scriptural positions while maintaining that, in ultimate truth, there are neither bodies nor non-bodies, and that the three bodies emerge only in conventional truth according to perceptual capacity and causal conditions. This analysis has direct implications for modern scholarly debates concerning whether Kuiji endorsed a "single-body" interpretation of Amitābha or affirmed the existence of an enjoyment body and corresponding Pure Land. The paper argues that Kuiji's grammatical and logical framework resists reductive readings, instead articulating a relational and perspectival model of buddhahood grounded in Yogācāra epistemology and exegetical practice.

Keywords: Kuiji; Yogācāra; trikāya; Pure Land Buddhism; Amitābha; Buddhist philology; Sanskrit compounds; hetuvidyā

Introduction

Interested parties including sectarian Buddhists of the Tang Dynasties and current scholars of Buddhist Studies have considered the essay *Forest of Meaning of Three-bodies* by Kuiji (窺基 632–682) to be an influential part of an ongoing debate about whether ordinary people with little or no training in or understanding of the Buddha-Dharma can experience the bliss of the Pure Lands of Amitābha, Maitreya or others. A number of sūtras and commentaries say that one has to be at the level of the bodhisattva stages to experience the Buddha's enjoyment body, yet scores of laypeople in Kuiji time were as today embracing the idea that one only has to chant the name of Amitābha to experience his paradise. The writers on Kuiji's essay today, primarily Japanese scholars, debate about whether he propagated a "single body theory" holding that Amitābha Buddha is only a historical *nirmāṇakāya* manifestation, or if such Buddhas also have or only have an enjoyment body, *saṃbhogakāya*, and a corresponding Pure Land. In this paper, I explore Kuiji's innovative approach to trikāya theory in his *Forest of Meaning of Three-bodies*, through his application of Sanskrit grammar, doctrinal interpretation, and hetuvidyā logic.

1. Sanskrit Grammar

In the first section titled "The Names of the Bodies," Kuiji employs an analysis of Sanskrit grammar to explain the different aspects of Buddha-bodies. This section is crucial because it lays the groundwork for his doctrinal interpretations that follow.

Kuiji begins by describing the names of each of the three bodies, citing various texts to define them. For example, he refers to the *Golden Light Sutra*, which states, "All tathāgatas have three bodies: 1) a transformation body, 2) a response body, and 3) a Dharma body. These three embody the supreme enlightenment of Anuttarā Samyak Saṃbodhi."¹

In his analysis, Kuiji uses Sanskrit compounds to explain the names and functions of Buddha-bodies. He categorizes these compounds into several types, outlined as follows:

Table 1 - Schematic comparison:

1. Mutually Dependent Words (*karma-dhāraya*), Chinese: *chí yè shì* 持業釋

Kuiji gives two examples of the names related to buddha-bodies that can be interpreted as this kind of compound: "Dharma-body (*dharmakāya*) and "dharma-nature" (*dharmatā*). He writes:

Because it is not like other bodies that are formed as a collection [of aggregates], but because it is their basis, it is called "body." Intrinsic nature (*svabhāva*) is precisely "body." This is the explanation in terms of mutually dependent words in a compound.² 'Dharmas' refers to the various different virtuous merits. "Nature" means the "fundamental essence." Because it means "essence," it is called "*dharmata*" (the nature of dharmas, *fǎxìng* 法性). The *Wuxing Commentary* [on the *Compendium of the Great Vehicle*] says, "Because *dharmata* is identical to the body, it is called the Dharma Body."³ Alternatively, "Dharmas" are precisely all conditioned virtues. In these ways, because it is the essential nature of dharmas, it is called dharma-nature (*dharmata*).⁴

2. Principal Component and Qualifying Components (*tat-puruṣa*), Chinese: *yī zhǔ shì* 依主釋

¹ *The Golden Light Sutra* T0664_16.0362c18 – c 20; Kuiji's *Forest of Meaning of Three-bodies* T1861_45.0358c24 - c26.

² This is a type of phrase in Sanskrit: compound words where there is equality of dependence between the terms.

³ T1598_31.0436a02. The passage Kuiji quotes reads: "Because *dharmata* is identical to the body, it is called the Dharma Body. Alternatively, it is called the Dharma Body because it is that which all dharmas depend."

⁴ T1861_45.0359a01 - a05.

Kuiji gives an alternative interpretation of the two examples "Dharma-body (*dharmakāya*) and dharma-nature (*dharmatā*) when seen as a compound of words that contains a principle component and qualifying components. He writes:

The *Wuxing Commentary* [also] says, "Alternatively, it is called the Dharma-body because it is that on which all dharmas depend."⁵ The *Cheng weishi lun* says, [It is called "Dharma-body"] because it is the basis of the great merit of dharmas.⁶ The *Sutra of the Buddha-stage* says, "Because it is the basis of the great merit of dharmas powers, fearlessness, and so forth, it is called *dharmata*. This is the reading of the term as a compound of words that contains a principle component and qualifying components, that is, "body" contains these three meanings.

Kuiji notes that *sambhogakāya*" is both 1 and 2 above as follows:

The *Cheng weishi lun* explains about the body of enjoyment for oneself saying, "It always enjoys for oneself the vast and great bliss of the Dharma."⁷ In terms of the body for the enjoyment of others, *sambhogakāya* is generally explained as the exposition of the Dharma for beings in the ten [bodhisattva] stages. It resolves the web of many doubts, causing others to experience joy. The combination of these two types [i.e., for enjoyment by oneself and for enjoyment by others] is called the enjoyment body. "The body of enjoyment by oneself" (*zì shòuyòng shēn* 自受用身) is a compound of words where there is equality of dependence between the terms. Therefore, "enjoyment," *shòuyòng* 受用, is exactly "body," *shēn* 身. "The body of the enjoyment of others," *tā shòuyòng shēn* 他受用身, is a compound of words that contain a principle component and qualifying component.⁸

3. Compound of Words with Different Concepts (*dvandva*), Chinese: *xiāng wēi shì* 相違釋

Kuiji writes: "The *Commentary on the Sūtra of the Buddha-stage* explains, "The transformation manifestation (*biànhuà* 變化) itself is precisely the subsequent transformation body (*biànhuà shēn* 變化身). Desiring to benefit and comfort sentient beings, it displays appearances in various events of transformation (*biànhuà shì* 變化事). The replacement of the old form is called transformation, 變 *biàn*."⁹ Being nonexistent and instantly existing is called manifestation 化 *huà*. "Transformation," 變 *biàn*, and "manifestation," 化 *huà*, are different when reading the expression as a compound of words that are composed of two different concepts.

4. Enumerative Compound (*dvigu*), Chinese: *dài shù shì* 帶數釋

⁵ T1598_.31.0436a03.

⁶ *Cheng weishi lun*, T1585_.31.0057c24.

⁷ *Cheng weishi lun*, T1585_.31.0057c27 – c28.

⁸ T1861_.45.0359a13 - a16.

⁹ *Commentary on the Sūtra of the Buddha-Stage*, T1530_.26.0325c08 – c10.

Kuiji says examples of this can be found anytime a text enumerates the three bodies that jointly comprise the trikāya.

Kuiji's approach to analyzing these compounds assumes equivalence between Sanskrit and Chinese terms, even though the formal features of Sanskrit compounds, like case inflections, do not exist in Chinese. Despite criticisms from scholars including Jonathan Silk,¹⁰ who argue that Kuiji was not entirely comfortable with Sanskrit grammatical analysis, Kuiji's explanations demonstrate the importance of understanding the implicit syntactic relations within compounds. By doing so, he aimed to clarify the confusion between script and language in traditional Chinese exegesis. Along with Silk, Robert van Gulik¹¹ and Robert Sharf¹² expressed suspicion of Kuiji's understanding of Sanskrit grammar as referenced in some of his other essays. Some suggest that he uses the analysis, trendy at the time, to help to explain the different aspects of Buddha-bodies and possibly to bolster his argument by making a show of his academic skills. Teng Weijen disagrees, arguing that despite the lack of nominal and verbal inflections in Chinese and its non-phonetic nature, compound analysis is possible and fundamental in Chinese. Accordingly, by breaking down compound words and explaining the relationships between their components (e.g., "*svabhāva*" for intrinsic nature and "*kāya*" for body), he clarifies their meanings.

2. The bodies emanated

In the second section he titles "the bodies emanated," Kuiji describes what he sees as six correct but seemingly contradictory interpretations of what the three bodies are and how they come about. All of the interpretations rely on texts that Kuiji often cites for proof and in the end he finds that the principles behind all six are correct, even while criticizing some of the interpretations of them.

[1] According to the Kuiji, the first interpretation is that of Bhāviveka and others with similar views. Kuiji describes this view based on the *Yogācārabhūmi-śāstra* and the *Sutra of the Buddha-stage*, saying that the Tathāgata's bodies and lands are profound and subtle, neither existent nor non-existent, free from discrimination, transcending conceptual proliferation, and therefore not included in teachings about realms or places. Although Kuiji does not say so, this clearly opposes views found in certain other Buddhist texts including Pure Land sūtras. According to Kuiji's panjiao system based on the *Samdhinirmocana Sūtra* and described in his first essay on "General Characteristics" of his school, found in the *Forest of Meaning in the Mahāyāna Dharma Garden*, the content of such texts would have been from a previous era when the Buddha was not yet elaborating the full meaning of his teachings.

Kuiji goes on to say that according to this view, in ultimate truth, there are no bodies or non-bodies, so the idea of three kinds of bodies does not apply. However, in conventional truth,

¹⁰ Silk, "The Yogācāra Bhikṣu."

¹¹ van Gulik, Robert. *Siddham: An Essay on the History of Sanskrit Studies in China and Japan*, vol. 36. Sarasvati-Vihara Series. Nagpur: International Academy of Indian Culture, 1956.

¹² Sharf, Robert H. *Coming to Terms with Chinese Buddhism: A Reading of the Treasure Store Treatise*, Studies in East Asian Buddhism, 14. Honolulu: University of Hawai'i Press, 2002.

three bodies appear based on the sense faculties: dharmakāya representing the principle of emptiness; sambhogakāya representing the wisdom of emptiness; and nirmāṇakāya appearing for the benefit of sentient beings.

[2] The second interpretation holds that the Dharma-body is characterized solely by thusness. Among the eighteen realms comprising the world of the senses, that is, five "bodies" (*shēn* 身) such as smells, sounds, and so forth, five "body-possessors" (*shēn zhě* 身者) such as eyes, ears, and so forth, and eight receivers or experiencer-consciousnesses (*shòu zhě* 受者), only the last three—the sixth consciousness (*manovijñāna*), the seventh consciousness (*mānasvijñāna*), and the eighth consciousness (*ālayavijñāna*)—are included once they become untainted. These consciousnesses, along with their corresponding factors, constitute the body of enjoyment for oneself, increasing the Dharma through meditative absorption, wisdom, and compassion. Of the Buddha's four kinds of wisdoms,¹³ the wisdom that regards all things equally (*samatā-jñāna*), which is applicable to those in the ten stages of bodhisattva progress, manifests the body for enjoyment (*sambhogakāya*) by others and creates Pure Lands. The wisdom that accomplishes all things (*krtyānusthāna-jñāna*) manifests transformation bodies (*nirmāṇakāya*) and Pure Lands for those of the three vehicles. This means that people of the three vehicles who have not reached the bodhisattva stages do not perceive the Buddha's enjoyment body but only the physical and historical body, *nirmāṇakāya*.

[3] Kuiji says that the third interpretation has four variations and these comprise numbers three through six of his six interpretations. All four variations hold that the Tathāgata's meritorious bodies and Pure Lands include aggregates, places, and realms. Each of these includes both contaminated and uncontaminated elements.

The first of these variations that is the third of Kuiji's six interpretations says that both the *Yogācārabhūmi-śāstra* and the *Sutra of the Buddha-stage* identify the pure Dharma Realm (Dharmadhātu) as the self-nature body (*svābhāvakāya*), with the *Sutra of the Buddha-stage* further describing it as the thusness of purity. The *Mahāyānasamgraha* explains that transforming the *ālayavijñāna* achieves the self-nature body, while the *Treatise on the Scripture of Adorning the Great Vehicle* adds that transforming the eighth consciousness leads to mirror-like wisdom, one of the Buddha's four wisdoms. The wisdom of equality and wisdom of marvelous observing constitute the enjoyment body. The *Treatise* also highlights that the cognition of essential identity in a Pure Land manifests a Buddha body for Bodhisattvas, with observing cognition expounding the Dharma and dispelling doubts. These wisdoms benefit both oneself and others, and the transformation of evolving consciousnesses achieves the enjoyment body.

Kuiji objects to this interpretation but not to the texts they are derived from, saying:

If mirror-like wisdom is the self-nature body (*svābhāvakāya*), then this interpretation of meaning cannot be true. The *Golden Light Sūtra* explains that suchness and the wisdom of suchness are both named dharmakāya. If the root of conditioned virtues is explained as

¹³ Other sources say a Buddha has four kinds of wisdom.

mirror-like wisdom and this is the dharmakāya, then all four categories of true wisdom in that same sūtra should be the dharmakāya. Also, concerning the explanation that transformation of the evolving consciousnesses achieves the enjoyment body, if the cognition that accomplishes works is not the enjoyment [body], then it should not be transforming consciousness. If it is that the cognition that accomplishes works is the transformation [body], then as for the question from the *Samdhinirmocana-sūtra*, "Does the transformation body have a mind or is it without a mind," the sūtra should answer decisively that it does have a mind. That is to say that the Buddha's four wisdoms would therefore be a part of that body [nirmāṇakāya].

How can the sūtra explain that it cannot be said that [the transformation body] has a mind because it does not depend on a mind of its own and that that it cannot be said that it does not have a mind because it has the mind that depends on others?¹⁴ Based on this, the transformation body does not consist of real wisdom. In this way, in contemplating the Buddha's body, there is a difference between the principle and the phenomena, between coarse and subtle virtues, single in essence but diverse in function, separately explained as three. How can it be said that they are divided into four kinds of cognition, each separately constituting a body?¹⁵

[4] The fourth interpretation, as taken from the *Cheng Weishi Lun*, again holds that the pure dharmadhātu is the self-nature body. Supported by the *Treatise on the Scripture of Adorning the Great Vehicle*, the self-nature body is described as inherently eternal, and, as stated in the *Treatise Praising the Buddha*, the self-nature body does not arise or cease. According to Asaṅga's *Treatise on the Diamond Sūtra*, upholding and expounding the virtues of the *Diamond Sūtra* leads to realizing the Buddha's Dharma body and the other two bodies. Asaṅga quotes the *Diamond Sūtra* in saying, "All Dharmas of all Buddhas emerge from this sūtra. All Tathāgatas originate from this sūtra."

According to the interpretation, the Dharma body, in its true nature, does not contain cognition. There are two types of enjoyment bodies: for oneself and for others. The merit that arises from the Buddha's mirror-like wisdom pervades the material body for one's own enjoyment. The *Treatise on the Scripture of Adorning the Great Vehicle* says that indeed, the great mirror-like wisdom is the Buddha's enjoyment body. The *Mahāyāna-saṃgraha* says that by transforming the various consciousnesses including the *ālayavijñāna*, the enjoyment body is achieved.¹⁶

Kuiji objects to and explains this interpretation as follows:

¹⁴ This is a provisional and unreal mind of the Buddha's transformation body.

¹⁵ T1861_.45.0359c09 - c20.

¹⁶ *Treatise on the Buddha-stage Sūtra*, T1530_.26.0326a18 - a20. *Cheng weishi lun*, T1585_.31.0058a25.

The *Mahāyāna-saṃgraha* explains that it is through transformation that the dharmakāya is revealed. It does not explain how the enjoyment body is attained. Since it explains the dharmakāya as neither arising nor ceasing, that it is only the realization of causes, and is not physical, mental and so forth, the category of mirror-like wisdom contradicts this. If it [mirror-like wisdom] is not the enjoyment body, then to which body does it belong? The enjoyment body encompasses the Buddha's unique conditioned virtues. Therefore, the wisdoms of the Buddha actually have form and mind, all for one's own enjoyment. The Buddha's [saṃbhogakāya] body for enjoyment by others is a manifestation of his wisdom of equality.

The characteristics of the various types of [nirmāṇakāya] bodies according to the class of being are manifested by the Buddha's wisdom that accomplishes all. Although it is said that the transformation body contains supreme wisdom, it seems that wisdom manifests or wisdom arises. This explanation of wisdom is called "substantial body with no cognition." It only explains that the wisdom of equality can manifest the enjoyment body, and the cognition that accomplishes work manifests the transformation body in the three activities. It does not say that the two bodies are the same as those kinds of cognition. Therefore, the two real wisdoms are encompassed by the enjoyment body for oneself. The two manifested characteristics are explained as the two [enjoyment] bodies.¹⁷

In short, Kuiji is saying that it is not "thinking" that produces the bodies and that the bodies produced are not the thinking itself as implied in the previous interpretation. Instead, it is due to the merit of the Buddha's wisdom that bodies manifest.

[5] Kuiji says that the *Golden Light Sutra* intends to explain that the pure dharmadhātu, along with the four types of wisdom and the eternal and pervasive form body with true, conditioned, and unconditioned virtues, is named the dharmakāya. Rooted in these virtues and corresponding to the tathāgatas' suchness, wisdom of suchness, and the power of the vow, the primary and secondary marks along with the aura around behind the Buddha's head are manifested for those before the ten grounds, those of the three vehicles, and for bodhisattvas of the ten grounds, forming the Response Body. This body, manifested for others' enjoyment, is called the response body because it appears in response to others' capacities, fulfilling the Buddha's vow without constraints of time or place, and manifests in the five destinies according to sentient beings. The transformation body includes both unmanifest and revealed forms, with the five destinies transformation body also considered to be a part of it. The enjoyment body for others, also called a response body, manifests transformative matters through supernormal cognition. The body of enjoyment for oneself is experienced personally by the Buddha, not in response to others. Both enjoyment bodies, though distinct in how they bring pleasure, are called *saṃbhogakāya*. The enjoyment body for oneself, rooted in conditioned virtues and not shared with other, is a distinct entity, and is not the true nature of dharmas or the dharmakāya. According to the *Golden Light Sutra*, each type of individual experiences the bodies from a different perspective without contradiction.

¹⁷ T1861_.45.0360a05 - a16.

[6] Kuiji describes the sixth interpretation as follows:

The *Sutra of the Buddha-stage* explains that the pure dharmadhātu is the self-nature body [svābhāvakāya], with the four wisdoms inherently shared, the eternal and pervasive material body with true merit, is the body for enjoyment by oneself, due to being cultivated over three incalculable eons. In the first fascicle of the *Treatise on the Sutra of Adamantine Transcendent Wisdom* by Vasubandhu, it is also named the "reward buddha." This is manifested for the bodhisattvas of the ten grounds. One part with subtle characteristics is for the enjoyment of others, for the joy of the Dharma for all Bodhisattvas. How could it be manifested for those of the three vehicles?¹⁸

Kuiji concludes that the principles of the first three interpretations conflict, as clearly shown in the discourse. The fourth and sixth interpretations, while slightly different in wording, do not conflict in principle. The fourth interpretation explains two kinds of wisdom as encompassing two bodies, not as two separate bodies but as manifestations of wisdom. Though the texts they use may seem different at first glance, they are not.

3. Hetuvidyā Logic

In the fourth section of Kuiji's essay, titled "Causes and Effects," he adapts hetuvidyā logic to discuss the causal relationships and characteristics of Buddha-bodies. Hetuvidyā is a system of Buddhist logic developed by Dignāga and others focusing on the principles of valid reasoning and inference. It is referenced in Xuanzang's *Cheng weishi lun*, which Kuiji references in his application of it to three-bodies theories. Kuiji applies this logic to explain how the three Buddha-bodies are related through causes and effects. He begins by stating the following:

These three bodies are not definitively separate or unified. The body for enjoyment by oneself serves as the self-manifest form. The dharmakāya is the essence of this body's principle, whose deep and profound wisdom is not known to others. When the three vehicles perceive it roughly, it is termed the transformation body. When perceived finely in the ten grounds, it is called the body for enjoyment by others. Due to different views, their characteristics differ, and virtues and principles gather and divide into three bodies. It is not as if they are three types of sentient beings each existing independently.¹⁹

Kuiji explains that the dharmakāya represents the ultimate truth or essence of Buddhahood. It embodies the profound wisdom that is not accessible to others. The saṃbhogakāya, or enjoyment body, is perceived by advanced practitioners and bodhisattvas. The nirmāṇakāya, or transformation body, appears to ordinary beings and those of the two vehicles. See Table 2 below.

¹⁸ T1861_.45.0360b24 - b29.

¹⁹ T1861_.45.0365b22- b27.

Table 2: Kuiji's description of Buddha-bodies adapted for canonical texts

He further elaborates on the relationship between these bodies by applying the ten causes found in the *Cheng weishi lun* including generative cause (Sanskrit: *upapattihetu*, Chinese: *sheng yin* 生因), projective cause or inductive cause (Sanskrit: *ākṣepakahetu*, Chinese: *yin yin* 引因 or 牽引因), awareness cause, also called illuminative cause (Sanskrit: *jñāpakahētu*, Chinese: *le yin* 了因), principle cause, and wisdom causes from hetuvidyā logic. Kuiji writes:

There is no definitive answer to whether the bodies have differences or are undifferentiated. They are neither definitively one nor different. For instance, as seen in the ten grounds, the body of Śakyamuni Buddha is named the body for enjoyment by others; as seen by the two vehicles, it is called the transformation body. The nondiscriminating cognition, upon observing the true principle, is termed the Dharma body. True wisdom, profound and subtle, having been long cultivated, brings about the bliss of enlightenment that the Buddha enjoys himself, not known to others, and is called the enjoyment body. Views differ and these are not definitively one in the same or different, but there are generative and awareness causes of the resulting characteristics. In this way, there is one result derived from two causes: one is the generative cause, and the other is the attractive cause.²⁰

Kuiji uses generative cause to describe how various practices and teachings lead to the manifestation of the Buddha's physical forms and qualities. The projective cause explains how these manifestations attract and transform sentient beings. He provides an example from the *Cheng weishi lun* and comments on it as follows with my clarifications added in brackets:

According to the *Cheng weishi lun*, "The power of these seeds [i.e., external seeds that are produced by the mind and are not real] to generate true fruit is called generative cause. [The power of these seeds] to pull in distant and decaying fruits [i.e., things that appear external to the observer and things that appear to have passed and faded away] (and cause them to not immediately terminate) is called attractive cause."²¹

The enjoyment body is like this. Before the adamant absorption, various distant untainted seeds are attractive causes. Seeds that are close to one's position [i.e., close in one's mind as opposed to appearing to be external and distant] are generative causes.

²⁰ T1861_.45.0365b28 - c01.

²¹ *Cheng weishi lun*, T1585_.31.0009c02.

In regard to a buddha's Dharma-body, both near and distant wisdom are attractive causes. There is no generative cause [i.e., the dharmakāya is not produced]. Therefore, one does not speak of inductive causes, produced causes, and so forth in attaining release. Instead, one only speaks of triggering causes (Sanskrit: *āvāhaka-hetu*, Chinese: *yinfa* 引發, initiating or triggering), clearly distinguished causes (定異因, 定別因 (Skt. *pratiniyama-hetu*), and so forth in attaining the unconditioned.

The various types of transformation bodies are of the rank of current manifestations. Seeds are generative causes because they produce correctly [i.e., right away]. In regard to śarīra relics, etc., they are called attractive causes, because they bring residual effects later.

Now, in the discussion of the enjoyment body [above], there is one result with two causes [i.e., attractive causes and generative causes]. If speaking of the Dharma body, there is one result and one cause [i.e., it is the fruit of liberation from bondage]. If speaking of the transformation body, there is one cause with two results [i.e., immediate and residual results]. Furthermore, the Buddha attains two results from two causes, namely, principle and wisdom causes.²²

Near the end of the section on causes and effects, Kuiji explains that there are ten causes as described in the *Cheng weishi lun*. In summary, his application of hetuvidyā logic to Buddha-bodies involves analyzing the causes that lead to the manifestation of each of the three bodies and their impact on sentient beings. This innovative use of the ten causes aims at providing a deeper understanding of how the Buddha-bodies function and interact, supporting Kuiji's larger thesis about who can perceive each of the respective bodies.

Table 3:

Causes and Effects of Each of the Three Buddha-Bodies

1. Dharma Body (Dharmakāya)

- **Attractive Causes:**
 - Both near and distant wisdom.
 - Initiating or triggering causes (Sanskrit: *āvāhaka-hetu*, Chinese: 引發 *yinfa*).
 - Clearly distinguished causes (Sanskrit: *pratiniyama-hetu*, Chinese: 定異因, 定別因).
- **Generative Causes:**
 - There is no generative cause for the Dharma body as it is not produced.
- **Effects:**
 - The nondiscriminating cognition, upon observing the true principle, is termed the Dharma body.
 - The fruit of liberation from bondage.
 - One result and one cause (attractive causes).

²² Kuiji's *Forest of Meaning of Three-bodies*, T1861_.45.0365c01 - T1861_.45.0365c13.

2. Enjoyment Body (Sambhogakāya)

- **Generative Causes:**
 - Practices and teachings lead to the manifestation of the Buddha's physical forms and qualities.
 - Various distant untainted seeds before the adamant absorption.
 - Seeds close to one's position (in one's mind).
- **Attractive Causes:**
 - Manifestations that attract and transform sentient beings.
 - Seeds that are distant and decaying, pulling in distant and decaying fruits and preventing them from terminating immediately.
- **Effects:**
 - The bliss of enlightenment that the Buddha enjoys himself, not known to others.
 - One result derived from two causes (generative and attractive causes).

3. Transformation Body (Nirmāṇakāya)

- **Generative Causes:**
 - Seeds that produce correctly and immediately.
 - Various practices and teachings leading to the manifestation of the Buddha's physical forms and qualities.
- **Attractive Causes:**
 - Śāstra relics, etc., which bring residual effects later.
 - Manifestations that attract and transform sentient beings.
- **Effects:**
 - Viewed by the two vehicles as the transformation body.
 - Immediate and residual results.
 - One cause with two results (immediate and residual).

Conclusion

Kuiji's analysis of the Buddha-bodies in this text, grounded in his use of Sanskrit grammar, doctrinal synthesis, and hetuvidyā logic, reflects his innovative approach to Buddhist exegesis. In terms of how he engages with the Sui and Tang debate, Kuiji maintains throughout his essay that in ultimate truth, there are neither bodies nor non-bodies. However, in conventional truth, where they appear according to sense faculties, it is said there are three bodies. Particularly in regard to sambhogakāya and nirmāṇakāya, doctrinal sources differ on how these bodies appear and which body each category of aspirant sees. While acknowledging these different perspectives in the second section of his essay on the bodies emanated, Kuiji's analyses by Sanskrit grammar and hetuvidyā logic endorse the idea that if people who have not attained the bodhisattva grounds see a buddha-body, it must be *nirmāṇakāya*. On the other hand, it is difficult to conclude definitively along which modern researchers including Hayashi Kana that Kuiji promoted a single body view of Amitābha considering such statements as found in the "causes and effects" section above,

"There is no definitive answer to whether the bodies have differences or are undifferentiated. They are neither definitively one nor different."²³

²³ Hayashi Kana. *Ji no busshin butsudo-ron: Tokuni amidahotoke no hotoke-kaku no hantei ni tsuite* 基の仏身・仏土論：特に阿弥陀仏の仏格の判定について (Kuiji's Buddha-body and Buddha-land Discourses, especially on the determination of the Buddhahood of Amitābha Buddha). *Shūkyō kenkyū*, Vol. 79 no. 3, 2005, 745-767.